

Legal & Ethical Policy Recommendations

MAY 2025

EUROPEAN IDENTITY THEFT OBSERVATORY SYSTEM

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Policy Recommendations

1 Survey and official statistics

Need for **more comprehensive EU surveys and official statistics** on the topic of identity-related crimes online. This exercise should aim at providing detailed information over each **specific crime** falling under the umbrella term of online identity theft.

2 Ethics, Data Protection and AI assessments

Clarify the role of Ethics, Data Protection and AI assessments in research projects beyond the proposal's screening.

3 Harmonization of E-Evidence Documentation Through Data Protection Obligations

There is currently significant **inconsistency** in how law enforcement agencies document the processing of personal data, both in the context of criminal proceedings and in broader crime control activities (e.g., detection and prevention). The EU Directive 2016/680, which concerns the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by competent authorities, holds potential **to promote greater harmonization**. This can be achieved if the requirements related to the Record of Processing Activities (Article 24 of the Law Enforcement Directive) and Logging (Article 25 of the LED) are properly implemented.

4 Examine the role of the Law Enforcement Data Protection Officer (LED DPO) as a structural guarantee for data protection.

The processing of information and data for the purposes of prevention detection, investigation and prosecution of crime must be lawful. The **LED DPO** is an **unexplored harmonizing opportunity** for ensuring the adherence to data protection principles in law enforcement activities. While some studies have explored the figure of the DPO in corporate or general frameworks, there is a significant gap in empirical research on DPOs within law enforcement.

Policy Implications

1 Survey and statistics

Provides policymakers and stakeholders with **reliable data** to craft targeted interventions. Enhances **understanding of trends and impacts** of identity-related crimes, enabling **tailored prevention and response strategies**. Strengthens **collaboration** across EU Member States by establishing **shared benchmarks and metrics**.

2 Ethics, Data Protection and AI assessments

Reduces overlaps and confusion by delineating responsibilities for ethics, data protection, and AI assessments. **Improves the rigor and value** of ethical assessments beyond box ticking. Foster trust in research outcomes by involving specialized experts (e.g. philosophers, legal scholars, AI experts). **Ensures** that ethics considerations are **consistently applied** throughout the project lifecycle, not just during the proposal stage.

3 Procedural admissibility of e-evidence through the harmonization documentation obligations in data protection obligations.

Documentation is widely recognized as essential for verifying the lawfulness and accuracy of operations conducted by law enforcement agencies. Given the nature of digital data, **concerns** often arise regarding its **potential alteration and the integrity of the evidence**—issues that can undermine the reliability and authenticity of the information presented in legal proceedings. The harmonization of obligations related to data processing records and logs, as outlined in Articles 24 and 25 of EU Directive 2016/680, can **enhance the procedural admissibility of e-evidence**. By promoting transparency, accuracy, and precision, such harmonization ensures that **relevant information is accessible to all parties involved**—most importantly, to the defense.

4 Examine the role of the Law Enforcement Data Protection Officer (LED DPO) as a structural guarantee of e-evidence.

In the specific context of e-evidence, the LED DPO could **address problems of traceability and controllability of data**, and by doing so, help **test its authenticity and reliability at court**. This is particularly relevant with regards to the controller's data processing record and logging obligations, and in general, with the compliance with data protection principles.

Project Details

Project Name

The European Identity Theft Observatory System (EITHOS)

Coordinator

DR Dimitrios ZARPALAS
CERTH

Programme - call topic

HORIZON-CL3-2021-FCT-01-12
Online identity theft is countered

Duration

3 years
October 2022 - September 2025

Budget

€ 2,996,141.25

Social Media

EITHOS_EU

eithos_eu_project

Eithos - Horizon Europe project

EITHOS_EU

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